

INTERLAMINAR CRACK DETECTION IN GRAPHENE NANOPATELET/ CFRP COMPOSITES USING ELECTRIC RESISTANCE CHANGE

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1 General introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced composites (CFRP) are extensively utilized in many industries due to their remarkable mechanical properties and light weight. One recent industry utilizing such composites is oil and gas. Notwithstanding, FRP laminates are critically susceptible to delamination, often initiated due to invisible interlaminar cracks. Such flaws in turn weaken the overall strength and stiffness of the material, thus reducing its in-service life and reliability. Consequently, it is desirable to develop an effective in-situ structural health monitoring technique that could prevent potential catastrophic failures in composite structures.

Most conventional nondestructive damage detection methodologies are not considered as “real-time based” techniques. Methods such as the X-ray, ultrasonic scanning, thermography, as well as those methods that require utilization of piezoelectric sensors or optical fibers, either require expensive equipment and/or skilled operators, thus are relatively costly. In some cases, the addition of sensors within laminates could potentially increase the likelihood stress-riser regions, further exasperating structure’s health.

The electrical resistance change (ERC) is a unique method that does not require implementation of additional sensors for detecting damage; however, it requires conductive materials like carbon. Several comprehensive research works have been performed in relation to damage detection of CFRPs using ERC (see for instance [1-3]). Virtually, all the research works conducted thus far have indicated that CFRPs are electrically anisotropic, and the electrical conductivity through the thickness of such materials becomes a function of the electrical contact resistance amongst the layers. This indicates that the through-thickness conductivity is considerably lower

than that along the fiber direction. Therefore, through-thickness damage (delamination) detection in laminates is more challenging in comparison to the types of damage that occurs along the fiber direction (e.g., fiber breakage). Therefore, increasing the through-thickness electrical conductivity of laminates could positively enhance the accuracy of interlaminar damage detection [4].

To increase the electrical conductivity of CFRP laminates, their matrix’s electrical conductivity could be improved. Several types of nano particles have been considered by various researchers to improve the electrical conductivity of various matrices (e.g., nano silver) [5, 6].

Emerging carbon nano-particles (CNPs) such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon nano-fibers (CNFs), buckyballs (C60) and graphene nanoplatelet (GNPs) have introduced a new generation of multi-purpose modifiers with outstanding mechanical, electrical and thermal properties [7-9]. However, the main challenges of fabricating CNP nanocomposites are the production cost of CNPs and the cost associated with the effort required to disperse CNPs in the resin.

Since the discovery of the GNPs, the investigations have mainly focused on fabricating nanocomposites using GNPs due to their lower cost and simpler manufacturing method compared to CNTs [10]. The multi effects of GNPs when added to the resins have been assessed experimentally [11-15] and some theoretical and semi empirical models have been developed to predict the elastic modulus and the electrical conductivity of GNP nanocomposites [16-17].

In this research, the effect of graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) as a means for enhancing the electrical conductivity of epoxy resin was firstly assessed and then, improving the ERC-based detection of invisible delamination in such laminates, was

investigated. Therefore, the main objective for the use of GNPs has been to increase the through thickness and transverse electrical conductivity of the host CFRP laminates.

2 Materials

Araldite LY 564 (Bisphenole-A epoxy resin) was mixed with Aradure 2954 (cycloaliphatic polyamine hardener) with weight ratio 100:35. LY564 is a hot cure and low viscosity (1200 *mPa.s*) epoxy resin. This epoxy system is available through Huntsman Co (west Point, GA).

The GNP considered as nano-filler in this research was xGnP-M-25, obtained from XG scientific (Lansing, MI). xGnP-M-25 has average thickness of 7 nm and an average particle diameter of 25 μm (Figure 1). The specific surface area of xGnP-M-25 is approximately 150 m^2/g . It has the density of 2.2 g/mL and the electrical conductivity of 10^7 Siemens/meter. It should be noted that the GNPs used in this study were in the form of as-received from the factory and no structural and chemical modification were done on the nano-particles.

The unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber fabric used in this research is available through Fiber Glast Corp. (Brookville, OH). This UD fabric is made without the use of typical hot melt process. Consequently, there is no crimping of the fibers and only minimal binder is used. The dry thickness of used UD carbon is 0.35 mm and it weighs 305 g/m^2 .

3 Specimen preparations

3.1 GNP/Epoxy nanocomposites

To fabricate the baseline test specimens (neat epoxy resin), Araldite LY 564 was mixed with Aradure 2954 hardener with the mentioned mixing ratio using a mechanical stirrer at 100 rpm for 10 minutes. Next, the mixture was degassed in a vacuum chamber at -28 *in-Hg* for 30 minutes, and then poured into molds. According to manufacturer's instructions, this resin should be cured at 100 °C for half an hour and then post-cured at 160 °C for 8 hours.

To fabricate the GNP-nanocomposite reinforced epoxy specimens (GNP-NCRE), firstly, the appropriate amount of GNPs were distributed into the resin using a mechanical stirrer at 2000 rpm for 15 minutes; then, the mixed GNPs were further dispersed into the resin using a three roll mill Lab model (Torrey Hill Technology, San Diego, CA). The roller rotating speeds were kept constant at 174, 84 and 31 rpm for apron, middle and feed rolls respectively for all specimens. The dispersion of

GNPs was promoted with roller gap distance of 40 μm for each GNP weight percent in resin (i.e., 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 wt%).

The dispersion process was repeated seven times for each concentration of GNP. After the dispersion, an appropriate amount of hardener was added to the resin and mixed using a mechanical stirrer set at 100 rpm for 10 minutes. The mixture was degassed in a chamber at -28 *in-Hg* for 30 minutes. Finally, the molds were poured and the GNP loaded resin was cured according to the aforementioned curing regime.

3.2 CFRP nanocomposite laminate fabrication

To fabricate the CFRP specimens, six layers of UD carbon fabric were cut with dimensions of 180 mm \times 180 mm and stacked on each other to obtain [0₆] laminate. The resin was injected into the fabrics using a VARTM setup for all CFRP laminates (i.e., CFRP laminates without and with GNP). Two virtual interlaminar crack zones were created by inserting two pieces of circular and thin Teflon layers with 10 mm diameter between layers 3 and 4 of the laminate during stacking process. Further information about the location of the interlaminar cracks will be provided in sections 4.2.

The laminates were cured for 2 hours at 60 °C and post-cured for 8 hours at 120°C. It should be noted that the weight percent of GNP in CFRP laminate was chosen based on the results reported in section 5.1. The GNP concentration by which the minimum electrical resistivity of nano-composite reinforced epoxy (NCRE) was obtained was assumed as the criterion of the selecting of GNP weight percent.

4 Test Methods

4.1 GNP/epoxy electrical resistivity

To measure the electrical resistivity of NCREs, a rectangular specimen with the dimensions of 60 mm \times 10 mm were cut from a 3 mm thick NCRE bar with the dimensions of 100 mm \times 20 mm. The through- thickness electrical resistivity of the neat epoxy and NCRE specimens with less than 1 wt% GNP was measured as per ASTM D257 [18]; and for remaining specimens, the electrical conductivity was assessed through the axial axes of the specimens as per ASTM D4496 [19].

A fixture was designed (see Figure 2) to facilitate measuring the electrical resistivity of NCRE specimens using the two-wire method. A highly accurate source/measurement unit (Keithley 2635B) was used to apply constant DC voltage of 100 volts

and the resultant current in specimens was measured. At least three specimens were tested for each weight percent of GNP content and all tests were carried out at room temperature (23 °C) at 50% relative humidity. Then, the volumetric electrical resistivity was calculated using Equation 1 [19]

$$\rho_v = R_v \frac{A}{L} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_v is the volume resistivity ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$); R_v is the volume resistance (i.e., the ratio of the DC voltage applied to the two electrodes on the specimens to the current distributed within the volume of the specimen, measured between the electrodes (Ω)); A is the effective cross-sectional area of the electrodes (cm^2) and L is the distance between the electrodes (cm).

4.2 Laminate ERC measurement

To assess the ERC in the laminates, specimens with dimensions of 125 mm × 125 mm × 2 mm were extracted from the base 180 mm × 180 mm × 2 mm laminate. The top and bottom surfaces of specimens were ground using sandpaper (roughness of 100) to facilitate direct contact between the electrical conductive tapes and carbon fibers in the laminates.

An addressable conducting network proposed by Takahashi et al [4] was used to find the location of invisible delamination. Conductive copper tapes were attached on each side of laminates. The width of each conductive line was 6 mm and the distance among the copper tapes was 25 mm. The direction of each conductive line located on the top surface of the laminates was parallel to the fiber direction, while those on the bottom surface were aligned perpendicular to the fibers' direction. The conductive bands were denoted one to six and A to F on the top and bottom surfaces of specimens, respectively. Figure 3a shows the entire experimental set up, including the specimen, used for assessing the ERC of CFRP.

A hole with 7.5 mm diameter was created through the thickness of laminate up to the Teflon layers in the mid-thickness of laminate using high speed milling machine and then, the machine speed was reduced to one tenth of its initial speed while the drill bit was constantly pressing the remaining layers (i.e., those under the Teflon layers) downward. As a result, an interlaminar crack (or delamination) was created around the hole. Figure 3b shows the

schematic of the setup by which the invisible delamination was created in CFRP laminates. One hole was created with coordinates in between conductive bands 4 and 5 on the top surface and in between conductive bands B and C on the bottom surface of the laminates. The second hole was created between (3,4) and (D,E) conductive bands. The electrical resistance between each pair of top and bottom conductive bands was measured based on the two-wire method by supplying 10 mA DC current using a highly accurate source/measurement unit, Keithley 2635B. A Multiplexer (Keithley 7011S) with a switch framework (Keithley 7001) were used to measure the resistance in a specific order between the contact pairs (see Figure 3c). A code was written in the Labview environment to control the experiment and to acquire and store the data.

5 Test Results and discussion

5.1 Electrical resistivity of NCRE

Figure 4 shows the electrical resistivity of the neat resin and the NCREs as a function of the GNP weight percent. NCREs with low concentration of GNPs show more or less the same resistance as the neat resin. Beyond 1 wt% GNP inclusion, the resistivity dramatically decreases. When the electrical resistivity of a NCRE suddenly decreases over a narrow range of filler concentrations, this threshold (i.e., filler volume fraction) is referenced as the “electrical percolation threshold” (EPT). In this study, the EPT was determined to occur at 1.2 wt% concentration of GNP.

The EPT depends on the filler size and the distance among the fillers. There are several analytical and semi-empirical models for predicting the EPT of nanocomposites such as the “exclude volume model” [20], Lu and Mai's model [21] and a recently proposed model based on the average interparticle distance (IPD) [17]. The latter model predicts the volume fraction of GNP at which the EPT would occur in NCREs by using Equation 2 [17].

$$V_{GNP} = \frac{27\pi D^2 t}{4(D + D_{IP})^3} \quad (2)$$

where V_{GNP} is the volume fraction of GNP, D is the nominal diameter of GNPs, t is the GNP thickness and D_{IP} is the specified length corresponding to electron hopping taking place between the adjacent conductive fillers and it could be set to 10 nm for

most types of the resins when GNPs with high aspect ratios are used [17].

The IPD model predicted the EPT to occur at 0.89 wt% GNP, while the experimental results show a deviation of approximately 25%. King et al [15] obtained similar EPT (1.48 wt %) as obtained in our experiments using GNPs with 15 μm diameter and 7 nm thickness. To further explore the cause of the discrepancy, a specimen previously used for evaluating the electrical conductivity of each GNP concentration was broken in half under a bending load and the fracture surfaces were assessed using the FE-SEM.

Figure 5a shows the fracture surface of the NCRE with 0.5wt% GNP concentration. The small arrows indicate the dispersed GNPs in the matrix. As evident, the distances among the GNPs are larger than the distance required for the electrons to be able to transfer from one GNP particle to another; as a result, the electrical resistivity of the NCRE is quite similar to that of the neat epoxy. Although distances among GNPs' in specimens with 1 wt% GNP concentration are less than those observed in the 0.5 wt% specimens (Figure 5b), nevertheless no GNP cluster was observed. It should be noted that the increase in the concentration of GNPs could increase the probability of GNP clustering. Figure 5c (1.5wt% GNP) and Figure 5d (2 wt% GNP) illustrate that the electrodes could potentially move easily within the clusters; as a result, the electrical resistivity of NCREs would be dramatically decreased.

Moreover, it is postulated that the average characteristic dimension of GNPs (i.e., GNP diameter), could play an important role on defining the percolation threshold of a NCRE. Smaller diameter GNPs would result in relatively higher EPT. Figures 6a, b, c and d also illustrate that the average size of the dispersed GNPs' diameter is less than 25 μm as per vendor's data.

5.2 Delamination detection

First, all the initial pair resistances (i.e., in the orthogonal direction) of the laminates without a delamination were evaluated (as the baseline data). Subsequently, the first hole and delamination were created with the procedure outlined in section 4.2. Then, the resultant resistances were measured in each pair of conductive contacts.

The color code map of pair resistance changes (PRC) of a typical laminate that hosted one delamination is shown in Figures 6a and 6b. Each color represents the PRC between the top and

bottom conductive bands. So, the entire area of laminate is shown by a 6 \times 6 matrix (i.e., 36 areas).

The resistance change at each pair of conductive bands was calculated by Equation 3.

$$RC = \frac{R'(tx, by) - R(tx, by)}{R'(tx, by)} \quad (3)$$

where RC is the PRC, R' is delamination hosting laminates' pair resistance (PR) and R is baseline laminates' PR (i.e., laminates without interlaminar crack). (tx, by) refers the pair resistance coordinate. For example, $(t1, bC)$ denoted the PR between the top conductive band 1 and bottom conductive band C.

As seen, the delamination caused the PRC to increase significantly. The through-thickness electrical conductivity of laminates is a function of electrical contact area of fibers in adjacent layers. Therefore, debonding among the layers of laminates interrupts the electron transfer from one layer to adjacent layer, which leads to high electrical resistance through the thickness of CFRP laminate.

To minimize the effect of system noise on delamination detection, the experimental results were passed through the following filter.

In the above flowchart e_m is the measurement error, ER_{max} is the maximum PRC of the laminate, ER_i is the maximum PRC of the area surrounding the

ER_{max} , ER_c is the minimum value for PRC to be considered as an evident for delamination and ER_p is the PRC at each pair of conductive bands.

The proposed filter compares the maximum pair resistance change with the measurement error of the system. When the value of ER_{max} is more than e_m the filter divides the mean value of RE_{max} and three other maximum PRC obtained in the area surrounding the ER_{max} by two, so to obtain the critical pair resistance value (ER_c). Each PRC that is more than ER_c could potentially indicate the existence of a delamination area.

The area surrounding the hole was obviously expected to show the highest PRC. Figure 6a illustrates that areas (5,C), (5,b), (4,B) and (4,C), which clearly show relatively higher PRC in comparison to the other areas. The sensitivity of the electrical resistance of the laminate with delamination was increased in the NCRE laminates (Figure 6b). The ERC measured in GNP-reinforced laminates is 27% higher than that of the laminate without GNPs. Furthermore, some areas around the areas with highest ERC in the GNP-reinforced laminates were observed to have higher PRC than the calculated ER_c . It worth noting that this phenomenon was not observed in laminates without GNPs. In the GNP-reinforced laminates, some of the GNPs would have contacts with carbon fibers of layers interface. As a result, the electrical contact resistance among the layers would be decreased. In other words, the improvement in conductivity obtained through the GNP reinforced resin increases the through-thickness conductivity of the laminate Takahashi et al [4] has demonstrated analytically that the sensitivity of the ERC method for delamination detection would increase dramatically if the transverse and through thickness electrical conductivities of laminates are improved.

It should also be noted that matrix cracking could not be observed in the laminates without GNPs, because the matrix would have low electrical conductivity and small cracks in matrix do not change the electrical resistance of laminates by a great margin. However, GNPs are essentially piezo-resistive materials; any change in a GNP's length (as result of either elongation/compression or bending) would cause a significant change in GNP's electrical resistivity. Matrix cracking could potentially bend or change the length of some of the GNPs. Thus, small or minor defects would be observable in laminate hosting GNPs (see Figure 6b).

Figures 7a and 7b show the areas containing two delaminations. The electrical resistance was marginally varied around the first hole but the ER change is still more than ER_c . This variation was obtained through the actual numerical values. Figures 6c, 6d, 7c and 7d are 2D contours of surface fitted on the obtained ERC results in this experimental research to determine the in visible delamination area in the laminate. The dark colors are indicative of the areas in which most likely the debonding exist, while the bright colors present the areas with potential matrix cracking.

6 Summary and conclusion

In this research, the effect of GNPs on the electrical conductivity of epoxy resin was assessed. Accordingly, the GNP loaded resin GNP was used to facilitate damage detection of an invisible flaw using the electrical resistance change method in CFRP laminates made by GNP-reinforced resin.

To assess the electrical conductivity of GNP/epoxy composite, GNPs with nominal diameter of $25 \mu m$ and thickness of $7 nm$ were dispersed with different weight percent in an epoxy. The results indicated that the electrical conductivity of CFRP laminates that were prepared by the GNP-reinforced epoxy resin dramatically decreased when the weight fraction of GNP exceeded beyond 1.5 wt%. This weight fraction is called the electrical percolation threshold of the GNP reinforced laminates.

The proposed ERC method could successfully distinguish the invisible delamination created around a hole in the laminates. But, the existence of GNPs increased the sensitivity of CFRPs to the electrical resistivity change resulting from delamination between the laminae and micro-cracks present in the matrix.

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Fig. 1. SEM image of X-GnP-25

Fig. 2. Two-probe electrical measurement fixture

(b)

Fig. 3. a) Experimental setup and the specimen b) Schematic of delamination creation setup c) Schematic of data acquisition setup

Fig. 4. Electrical resistivity of GNP/epoxy nanocomposite as a function of GNP content

10.0kV 11.0mm x1.00k SE(U) 50.0um

10.0kV 11.0mm x1.00k SE(U) 50.0um

Fig. 5. FE-SEM images of the fracture surfaces of electrical conductivity specimens. a) 0.5 wt%, b) 1 wt%, c) 1.5 wt% and d) 2 wt% of GNP

Fig. 6. ERC contours of the laminate with one delamination, without and with GNPs

